

MODELS OF INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOUR

1 Wilson's model of information seeking behavior

Wilson's models of information behavior have developed over a long period. The first set of models were published in 1981 and date back to a doctoral seminar presentation at the University of Maryland in 1971 when an attempt was made to amplify the processes involved in what was known at that time as 'users needs research'. Wilson presented a series of interrelated models in his 1981 paper that, to this day, still stands out as one of the most cited papers in the field. The review of the models presented by Wilson is clear: Wilson has advanced a threefold view of information seeking: the context of the seeker, the system employed, and the information sources that might be drawn up. Wilson's model is not derived from any theory but from an analysis of detailed human information behaviour. Wilson pointed out that information search behavior is a subset of information seeking behavior and that information seeking behavior is in turn only a subject of all possible information behavior. As such the existence of modes of information behavior, other than information seeking is implied, consequent upon analysis of various models, Wilson has suggested that various areas of research within the general field of information behavior may be seen as a series of nested fields

2) Dervin' model

Dervin's sense-making theory, having been developed over the past several decades, should not be regarded simply as a model of information-seeking behavior. As Dervin noted, it is, "a set of assumptions, theoretical perspective, methodological approach, set of research methods and practice designed to cope with information perceived as a human tool designed for making sense of a reality assumed to be both chaotic and orderly.". Dervin was, in fact one of the first researchers to formulate and apply the sense making approach to the needs of a common citizen. His work was based on a conceptual premise and related methodologies whereby he assessed how people can make sense out of their worlds and how they manage resources for problem resolution. However, sense making is conceptualized in terms of four consistent elements: a situation in time and space, which identifies the differences between the contextual situation and the desired situation; an outcome, that is consequences of the sense-making process and a bridge, that is some means of closing gap between situation, a gap bridge and outcome. Dervin has expressed these elements in terms of a triangle: situation, Gap/Bridge and outcome. The strength of Dervin's model is partly located in its methodological implications, since

for information behavior, it has a manner of questioning that might help unravel the nature of a problematic situation, the degree to which information services would bridge the gap of uncertainty, confusion, or whatever, and nature of the outcome from the use of information.

3 Ellis Model

David Ellis has defined information behavior in terms of sequences of activities undertaken by a user:

Starting: The strategies used by the user to initiate seeking information. It refers to activities characterizing the initial search, for instance, asking some colleagues.

Chaining: Pursuing footnotes or chains of citations or other modes of referential linkage between materials.

Browsing: Semi-directed or semi-structured searching in an area of potential interest. **Differentiating:** Using difference between sources as a filter on the nature and quality material examined.

Monitoring: Maintaining awareness of developments in a field through the monitoring of particular sources. It means keeping up to date.

Extracting: Selectively identifying relevant material in an information sources

Verifying ending: This may be defined as typing up loose ends through a final search

The strength of Ellis model is that it is based on empirical research and has been tested in subsequent studies. The behavioral model itself consists of the relation between these characteristics or components. These can interest in various ways in different information seeking patterns. It doesn't represent any group of phrases that one or any of the users pursue to find information. The existing model has been expanded or developed based upon studies related to the seeking behavior for information of a set of researchers including English literature researchers, physicists, chemists, engineers and research scientists in the industrial development environment.

4. Kuhlthou's Mode

The Kuhlthau model complements that of Ellis by attaching to stages of the information search process the associated feelings, thoughts, and actions and the appropriate information tasks. This association of feeling, thoughts, and action clearly identifies kuhlthou's perspectives as phenomenal rather than cognitive. The stages of information seeking behavior as per kuhlthou's model are:

1. Initiation
2. Selection
3. Exploration
4. Formulation

5. Collection
6. Presentation

5 Foster's non-linear model

Ongoing analysis of emergent concepts and their inter-relationship developed in clusters of behaviors, intervening factors, and contexts. Concepts were grouped into three core categories: Opening, Orientation, and Consolidation around which analysis continued to develop definitions, functions, information needs, and the contexts attributable to them.

The new model of interdisciplinary information-seeking is represented in terms of three core processes and three levels of contextual interaction. The next sections start with the outer layers of the illustration and move towards the core processes of Opening, Orientation, and Consolidation, finally culminating in a summary of the whole model

6. Kirkelas's Model of Information Seeking

The Krikelas model (1983) is an early model and was cited widely. The model contains thirteen components. It is a general model that is applicable to ordinary life. In the model the twin actions namely information gathering and information giving are given at the top. Information gathering is done along the line of deferred needs which may be triggered either by a situation or environmental setting where the individual involved requires accessing information. This model displays information received as being taken to the memory or person's personal files.

7 Johnson's Model

There are seven factors under three headings given in the Johnson's model (1987). The fundamental process flows from left to right. The four factors under the heading antecedents are grouped under two sub headings which are termed as background factor and personal relevance. The background factor includes the factors of demographics and personal experience and the personal relevance factor includes salience and beliefs. The second heading Information carrier factors include characteristics and Utilities of the information channels selected and used by the seekers. The last heading is information seeking actions.

Choo et al's (1998) behavioural model of information-seeking on the Web must be considered as an information retrieval model. The name of the model implies that it is a behavioral model. There are also several features in the model which are comparable with Aguillar's (1967) modes of environmental scanning. Choo integrated and developed Aguilar's modes of environmental scanning and Ellis's

information-seeking behavior model into a new behavioral model of information-seeking on the Web. Choo identified four main modes of information-seeking on the Web: undirected viewing, conditioned viewing, informal search and formal search. Being a hybrid model based on Ellis (1989) and Aguillar (1967), the Behaviour Model of Information Seeking on the Web shows the value of applying multi-methods in gathering data and can be extended or mapped to other information-seeking activities such as an information search. As such the model, now also provides a systematic method in order to examine the relationship between information needs, search strategies and search tactics.